

Development of Area Frame for Agricultural Statistics in Pakistan Using Satellite Remote Sensing

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Abstract

In agriculture, monitoring of crop growth and development, and early estimates of the final productions to be expected are of general interest for policy makers. This enables planners and decision makers to predict how much to import in case of shortfall or optionally, to export in case of surplus. Therefore, monitoring of crop development and crop growth, and early prediction are generally important. Censuses have always been the principal tools to acquire reliable statistical information. But a census is an enormous undertaking and requires a lot of resources. Area frame sampling developed to provide a multipurpose sampling frame, is an important aspect of modern survey design and probability sampling and is not a new technology. In fact, area frame sampling was first applied to agriculture in Iowa in 1938 and 1939 using aerial photography. Remote sensing data can provide alternative of this situation. So the development of Area Frame using satellite remote sensing requires no baseline data and will be accurate. So Area Frame sample design using satellite remote sensing can answer many questions of Pakistani agriculture statistics. In 1980 Pakistan Government started consulting on area frame development with USA, this technology still in use which has taken almost 20 years. Now SUPARCO National Space Agency of Pakistan has taken a step forward to develop high tech based "area frame development" to develop a full operational system for the estimation of agriculture statistics. Stratification is the first step for area frame development. Stratification is basically a process of grouping the homogenous areas in relation to the information available. This makes it possible to reduce the variance between the samples by introducing it within the samples. Each stratum should represent solely information inside it. This will make possible the estimation with less than 5 % variance. The primary polygons were ranging from 150ha to 10000 ha (100sq Km). Primary sampling unit (PSU) was a standard unit with range of 300-400 ha area inside it. Whereas TSU was a regiment with approximately area of 30 ha. Then all layer PSU's were again subdivided to standardize the PSUs for 300-400 ha. Standard numbering to each PSU was carried through software code programming in VB. This numbering was named as FDID. This numbering was carried out in "serpentine fashion" starting from north east and end in south west of the district. Main reason for such numbering was based a three aspects. This study shows that the use of satellite data for estimating and forecasting crop production is an exciting and effective technology. Building an area frame (AF) is a major investment. Satellite remote sensing (RS) data have proven to be quite effective in terms of quality, timeliness and cost. This study also shows the interaction between remote sensing and area sampling frame methods. It serves as a powerful supplement to on-the-ground techniques traditionally employed as well as other statistical methods being developed without area frame sampling or ground observations.

Introduction

In agriculture, monitoring of crop growth and development, and early estimates of the final productions to be expected are of general interest for policy makers. This enables planners and decision makers to predict how much to import in case of shortfall or optionally, to export in case of surplus. Since yield influences prices and subsidization it is also important on the farming level to reliably estimate its expected value as early as possible during the growing season. This enables the farmer to optimize return through optimized fertilizer/pesticide application or irrigation. In addition, realistic and timely estimates of yield expectation form the basis for monetary decisions in fields such as credit business and the stock exchange. Therefore, monitoring of crop development and crop growth, and early prediction are generally important. The formulation of food and agriculture policy, monitoring functions, agricultural planning, export and import planning, and agricultural project monitoring and evaluation usually requires governmental decisions. These decisions, in turn, necessitate support from effective information systems and statistics.

Censuses have always been the principal tools to acquire reliable statistical information. But a census is an enormous undertaking and requires a lot of resources. The tabulation of questionnaires can take years. This is also true for specialized censuses such as those specifically addressed to agriculture. Censuses are also error prone because of omissions and the difficulty in quality control on a large mass of data. It is common to use probability estimates to *true-up* the census because sampling errors associated with probability surveys are smaller than non-sampling errors associated with a census. Area frame sampling developed to provide a multipurpose sampling frame, is an important aspect of modern survey design and probability sampling and is not a new technology. In fact, area frame sampling was first applied to agriculture in Iowa in 1938 and 1939 using aerial photography.

Rationale

At the moment very little information exists regarding agricultural statistics in rural areas of Pakistan. Where it does exist, it is either outdated or very subjective and this is the case for the whole country. This implies that there is very little and subjective baseline data that can be used as an input for a survey and consequently an estimation of agriculture statistics. To obtain agricultural information by taking a complete enumeration of the population would not be feasible in a developing country like ours, which cannot afford the expense of a census in order to obtain agricultural statistics. Agricultural statistics are extremely demanding because crop cycles are in many cases three months or less in duration. Information about basic food supplies is crucial to a stable government. AF and associated advanced technologies have evolved over the years into a system that can generate accurate

statistics. Remote sensing data can provide alternative of this situation. So the development of Area Frame using satellite remote sensing requires no baseline data and will be accurate. So Area Frame sample design using satellite remote sensing can answer many questions of Pakistani agriculture statistics.

Remote Sensing as a tool for Agricultural Statistics

Remote sensing is a tool which has been around for a long time and has wide applications in agriculture. Remote sensing has greatly improved over the last few decades as the quality of digital imagery has improved.

Satellites have become an important part of modern information systems. Specialized personnel in Europe and the United States (U.S.) have been involved in the development of this technology since 1972 when Landsat 1 was launched. While we cannot cover all aspects of such development, we do present significant developments in this creative and useful technology. While state-of-the art technology is discussed in general terms, when appropriate, specific applications and their ramifications are provided in detail with special emphasis given to remote sensing. Today, data remotely sensed from satellites are applied to the construction of AF with a high degree of proficiency. Current technology has enabled the remote sensing experts to implement a variety of successful projects in diverse agricultural situations in a standardized manner and in relatively short time frames.

Satellite Remote Sensing can help us as at least three types of advanced tools that generate data about agricultural items and that should not be neglected by decision makers that need accurate and timely agricultural estimates.

- 1. Digital analysis** of satellite data improves the estimates of land cover and is used widely in Europe and USDA for crop hectare estimation. This method is presented in detail.
- 2. Multiple frame sampling (MFS)**, selects samples from two or more frames. While the main focus of this manual is on satellite remote sensing, an overview of MFS is presented.
- 3. Agro-meteorology models** are used to forecast crop yields. Results of these models are greatly improved when actual yield data are obtained and used in the calibration process. AFs can provide calibration data for agromet yield models. However, we do not present agromet yield models in this manual.

Study Area

In 1980 Pakistan Government started consulting on area frame development with USA, this technology still in use which has taken almost 20 years. Now

SUPARCO National Space Agency of Pakistan has taken a step forward to develop high tech based "area frame development" to develop a full operational system for the estimation of agriculture statistics.

Area frame is a sampling base on clustering concept an area frame sampling is suitable for general purpose sampling and is designed for obtaining information about variables associated with land especially crops, soil, forest etc. Even socio-economic aspect can also be determined especially rural poverty and its relationship with poverty status of the country. A district named Sheikhpura from Punjab province. Main reason for the selection is, it being representative of an agro-ecological zone and its cropping pattern. In Sheikhpura rice wheat is dominant cropping pattern. Total area of Sheikhpura is 5864 sq Km (586400 ha).

Methods and Procedures

The alternative to using a complete enumeration of a population would be to conduct a sample survey. This would cost the taxpayer less, could be conducted more efficiently, a greater scope of data might be sampled and, in some cases, may even be more accurate (Cochran, 1977). Area Frame sampling is a widely used methodology in countries like the USA and in Europe and consists of the following steps:

- Stratification - the distribution of livestock varies considerably over the province and magisterial districts. The precision of the survey estimates can be improved by dividing the land into homogenous groups or strata and then optimally allocating the total sample to the strata.
- Sampling - within each stratum, the land could be divided into the sampling units and then a random sample of these units is taken.
- Analyses - several decisions are made that can have an impact on the statistical and cost efficiency, e.g.strata definitions, allocation of the sample to the strata and the method of selecting the sample.
- Quality assurance - it must be ensured that no land is omitted from - or duplicated in - the frame and that the area has been properly stratified.

The advantages are versatility, being statistically sound, cost-effective, an ideal framework for a GIS, the fact that it can be implemented anywhere and that it has future value.

The disadvantages, however, are that it is less efficient than a complete list of the population, it is inadequate for rare items and the lack of sufficient boundaries and materials can be a problem.

Stratification

Stratification is the first step for area frame development. Stratification is basically a process of grouping the homogenous areas in relation to the information available. This makes it possible to reduce the variance between the samples by introducing it within the samples.

There are two important aspects regarding stratification which are as follows

- Stratums Definitions
- Construction of stratum based on physical boundaries from satellite images.

Figure1: Stratification of PSUs using physical boundaries

Stratums Definitions

This is a core stage during area frame development as all estimation will depend on its accuracy. SO each stratum should represent solely information inside it. This will make possible the estimation with less than 5 % variance.

We have used eight well developed stratum definitions to construct an area frame for Sheikhpura district that are as follows,

Stratum	Definition
11	Instance Cry Land Area (75-100 % Stratum)
12	Less intense crop land (50-75 % Stratum)
21	Cropland (25-50 %)
42	Cropland (<25 %)
31	Sub Urban area (Less that 50 houses \ Km ²)
32	Urban
50	Non farmland (desert, Forest, Saline)
60	Water (rivers canals)

Secondly the area frame based stratification was started using the SPOT 2.5m Pan and 10 m multispectral images. Firstly administrative boundary of Sheikhpura district was laid on SPOT image. Second step was to using the cut polygon feature function to make a digital layer on images along with respective physical boundaries. Major physical boundaries Include metaled raods, non-metaled roads, water, canals, field boundary, field paths, desert etc.

We first divided the large areas through main canals passing though the distirct. This was assigned stratification of 60 which also include river area. This enabled us to make further subdivision through physical boundaries. Similarly other stratification were identified on satellite images. Digitization work was done at 10,000 scale to identify the liner features based on visual interpretation. The polygons were made by the area with homogenous land features only. It took almost 8 working days to complete stratification for primary sampling units (PSU). Each polygon was give strata ID as defined above in its attribute table.

The primary polygons were ranging from 150ha to 10000 ha (100sq Km) to improve this standardization was laid down which mainly include two aspects.

- Primary Sampling Unit (PSU)
- Terminal Sampling Unit (TSU)

Primary sampling unit (PSU) was a standard unit with range of 300-400 ha area inside it. Whereas TSU was a regiment with approximately area of 30 ha. Then all layer PSU's were again subdivided to standardize the PSUs for 300-400 ha.

Standard numbering to each PSU was carried through software code programming in VB. This numbering was named as FDID. This numbering was carried out in "zig zag / snake fashion" starting from north east and end in south west of the district. Main reason for such numbering was based a three aspects.

- Adjacent PSU's must have similar homogenous conditions (Weather, soil etc)
- This will enable the systematic listing of all PSU's for all stratum.
- To ensure the wide distribution of PSU's on whole district in each stratum.
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Figure2: Classification of different Strata

Allocation of Samples

After unique numbering of all PSU's the important aspect was allocation of segments in each stratum. This was based on surface area under each stratum. For this attribute table of PSU's sample file was converted from "dbf" format to excel format. In excel format we convert PSU's area (in Ha) in total segment.

$$\text{Number of Segment} = \frac{\text{Total PSU's in ha}}{\text{Segment area (30ha)}}$$

Then we calculated total number of segments for all strata and this enabled us to calculate percentage contribution of each stratum on the whole district. We allocated the number of samples in each stratum based a percentage contribution. Final calculation for allocation of sampling is given in table.

Stratum	Area in ha	# of 30 Ha Segment	% age Contribution	# of sample
11	372870	12429	64.11	18
12	157260	5242	27.04	10
21	12810	427	2.20	2
31	32700	1090	5.62	2
42	5940	198	1.02	2
32				
13				2

So total 34 sample were finalized based on percentage contribution of stratum into total area of a district. So 64 % of area in Sheikhpura district remain under agriculture, this area is highly productive as it come under stratum 11 where that is more that 75 % crop land. This was the stratum which got maximum allocation of 18 segments.

Figure3: Classification of different Strata

Selection of PSUs

After allocation of number of segments to all PSU's based on probability proportionate area inside it and number of sampling units to each stratum based on a percent contribution of each stratum to overall area, next step is the final selection of sampling units through

- Sampling interval calculation (k)
- Random number

Sampling interval is simply calculated by dividing population with total number of samples i.e.

$$K = N \div n$$

Where N is population parameter and n is total number of sample units. For example the stratum total area is consist of 25000 segments and we have to select 10 segments as sample. The interval "K" will be

$$K = 25000 / 10 = 2500$$

Figure4: Selected PSUs with Stratum ID

This mean the random number will be in between 1 to2500. Random number is a number will equal probability of its occurrence. It also reduces biasness in selection procedure at any level of sampling.

In similar way each stratum interval "k" was calculated then random number was selected from random number table. In each stratum the selection was based on segment number arranged to each PSU and its FDID arranged number and cumulating of number of 30ha segments in side that PSU.

Conclusion

This study shows that the use of satellite data for estimating and forecasting crop production is an exciting and effective technology. Building an area frame (AF) is a major investment. Satellite remote sensing (RS) data have proven to be quite effective in terms of quality, timeliness and cost. This study also shows the interaction between remote sensing and area sampling frame methods. With satellite RS, an AF system of statistics can be implemented rapidly and reliably. The combined use of AF and satellite RS also allows collection of geocoded, land-cover information which can be useful for monitoring environmental parameters. While not replacing traditional data collection methods, remote sensing promotes efficient ground sampling. It serves as a powerful supplement to on-the-ground techniques traditionally employed as well as other statistical methods being developed without area frame sampling or ground observations.

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